

300 GHz finger measurement

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Abstract—We studied the effect of a finger and similar objects on channel gain in short distance propagation measurements at 220–330 GHz.

Index Terms—Terahertz, blockage, diffraction, propagation, measurements.

I. INTRODUCTION

Background... Inspiration by [1] and [2]...

The expectation is that propagation at the considered frequency is rather deterministic and follows well established formulas of transmission, reflection, and diffraction. It has been shown that ray tracing channel modelling methods provide good prediction capabilities at 60 GHz [3] and the same behaviour is anticipated at 0.3 THz frequency. We aim at collecting measurement based evidence to evaluate these expectations in the case of finger or similar small object blockage condition...

II. METHODS

The main contribution of this paper is in radio channel measurement and observations made on the results. In addition to that, we use also well known theoretical tools, like knife edge diffraction model and Fresnel ellipsoids, to asses measurement results. Actual modelling of the investigated phenomena is, however, left for future work. In the following subsection we describe the measurement system and after that we discuss briefly the theory used in evaluations.

A. Measurement system

[NUUTTI...]

A blocking object and the transmitter (Tx) antenna are shown in Fig. 1. The receiver (Rx) antenna is opposite to Tx at 350 mm distance from it. The positioner is not shown in the photograph. It is below the phantom hand, which is attached to it with a plastic stand. Coordinate system of the positioner is drawn in Fig. 1 with red arrows. Origin of the coordinate system is on the Tx antenna. The axis perpendicular to Tx-Rx line is labelled Y and the parallel axis is labelled X. The range of motion on Y and X axis is $-50 \dots 50$ mm and $5 \dots 165$ mm, respectively.

Calibration is done ... [NUUTTI, MITEN]. Fig. 3 depicts the calibrated transfer function of the measurement system. It is composed of the free space loss, which is approximately 72 dB, and antenna gains, which are 20.5 dB, at the centre frequency of measurement band. With identical horn antennas

Fig. 1. Photograph of the hand measurement. Coordinate axes are illustrated with red arrows.

at both link ends, this sums up to approximately -30 dB gain that is readable from Fig. 3. With fixed aperture at both link ends the total antenna gain over compensates the free space loss, as can be observed from the slightly increasing trend of transfer function in Fig. 3. The few decibel fluctuation is explained by [MILLÄ, heijastukset reunoista?]

[NUUTTI...]

With the measurement bandwidth of 110 GHz the achievable delay resolution is approximately 9.1 ps ($9.1 \cdot 10^{-12}$ s). In distance this correspond to propagation length resolution of 2.7 mm.

We recognize that the phantom hand used in measurement is not intended for the investigated frequencies...

It is noted that positions of different object are not perfectly comparable. The positioner itself has accuracy down to $\approx 10^{-5}$ mm, but the starting coordinates of the grid may have changed slightly from object to object. The system is lacking laser distance meters that would enable high precision positioning of newly attached objects.

B. Processing of measurements

Output of each measurement is a complex channel frequency response (CFR) $H(f, x, y)$ at certain object coordinates x, y . CFRs are converted to channel impulse responses (CIRs) $h(\tau, x, y)$ with the inverse Fourier transform. An example CFR without an object is depicted in Fig. 3. The corresponding CIRs is shown in Fig. 4 with yellow dotted line. The CIR has highest peak on the delay that represents propagation path length of 350 mm, which is the line of sight (LOS) distance between Tx and Rx.

Fig. 2. Photograph of the measurement system. [TÄTÄ KUVAA EN VÄLTTÄMÄTTÄ JÄTÄ TÄHÄN]

Fig. 3. Channel transfer function of the measurement system without blocking object. The magnitude per frequency is composed of antenna gains minus the free space loss.

There are multiple reflections between the object and Tx antenna. Our intention is mainly to study the blockage and diffraction effects of objects. More precisely, their impact on the channel gain. Thus we try to ignore (multiple) reflected paths by time gating the CIRs. The channel gain is determined as

$$G(x, y) = \sum_{\tau \in \tau_l} |h(\tau, x, y)|^2, \quad (1)$$

where τ_l is a set of delay bins close to the delay of LOS path. A reflection from the Tx antenna will be counted on eq. (1)

when the object is closest to Tx, but similar reflections may be present also with real devices. [This approach would need proper normalization to yield absolute gains of the calibrated channel. However, relative gains of different measurements are in our interest and they are maintained and revealed adequately by this method. ...]

C. Theoretical tools

[Tähän kirjoitellaan jotakin, jos ehditään. Ajattelin lähinnä laskea Fresnelin vyöhykkeiden kokoja eri etäisyyksillä ja pohtia onko niiden tukkeutuminen havaittavissa mittadatasta. Lisäksi ajattelin laskea veitsenterädiffraktiota ja katsoa saisiko niitä tuloksia jotenkin istumaan mitattujen polkujen voimakkuuksiin. ... Tähän siis tulisi kertaus tai maininta näistä teorioista. Analyysi tulisi sitten Results-kappaleeseen.]

III. RESULTS

In total six objects were measured, a phantom hand made of [MIKÄ MATERIAALI?], two metallic stripes, two cardboard stripes, and a rod made of teflon. Objects and their dimensions, width \times thickness for stripes and diameter for the rod, are defined in Table I. The thin cardboard strip is coated on one side and is matt finished on the other side. The corrugated cardboard has thin cardboard layers on both sides and a corrugated layer in between. The corrugations are horizontally oriented. The orientation of phantom hand is shown in Fig. 1. The index finger is not perfectly straight. All stripes were vertically oriented, such that broad sides are facing Tx and Rx. The rod is symmetric wrt. its axis. The axis was vertically oriented.

CIRs of all six objects in positions of $(x, y) = (5, 0)$ mm are depicted in Fig. 4. The highest peak without an object and with the two cardboard stripes is at 351 mm propagation delay, indicating the shortest path length. It is not well visible in the figure, but the gains of cardboard stripes at the shortest path are 1.2 dB below the clear case, thus the absorption loss of both cardboard stripes is only 1.2 dB. The phantom hand has a peak at the same 351 mm propagation length, but it is 51 dB attenuated as compared to the clear case. Another, slightly stronger peak occurs with 15 mm longer propagation length. The second path is possibly a constructive sum of a few diffracted paths that are reflected from the Tx horn. Evidently there is no transmission through the metallic stripes. Their strongest peaks occur at path lengths 25 to 50 mm longer than the LOS path.

The teflon rod provides 2.9 dB higher path gain and 10 mm longer propagation length than the LOS path in free space case. The rod acts as a lens and magnifies the path gain. The propagation speed inside teflon rod is slower, which explains the 10 mm \approx 33 ps increase in delay. Relative permittivity ϵ_r of teflon is 2.1. The increase in propagation length is $\sqrt{\epsilon_r}$. The rod has diameter of 26 mm. If it was a large slab with that thickness, the increase would be about 11.7 mm, which is close to the observed increment. Now the shape of rod has impact, and among other things it widens the transmission path as can be remarked from Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. CIRs of all objects at the closest position to Tx ($x = 5$ mm and $y = 0$ mm).

Channel gain as a function of finger coordinates is shown in three-dimensional (3D) plot of Fig. 5. Positions approximately between $y = -40$ and -20 mm are cases where the finger or the hand do not distract the transmitted signal. There the gain is at the level of -30 dB as in the no-object case of Fig. 3. On positive y values between 20 and 40 mm we can observe fluctuation of gain, especially when x increases and the hand is farther away from Tx. This probably results from interaction with other fingers of the phantom hand. Notice that the right side of axes in Fig. 5 and 6 is the left side in Fig. 1.

The same gain values (with phantom hand) are illustrated in a two-dimensional (2D) plot in Fig. 6. We can read that the lowest gain, -73 dB, occurs when the index finger is closest to Tx, i.e., when $y = 0$ and $x = 5$ mm. This corresponds to about 44 dB excess attenuation as compared to the case without the object. At the same y coordinates, when x increases up to 21 mm, the gain increases up to 60 dB, but is still lowest at $y = 0$ mm. Then further increasing x from 37 to 165 mm results in further increased gain at $y = 0$ mm. Now, however, the minimum gain occurs on different y positions symmetrically around the centre. This must be due to constructive combination of diffracted paths from edges of the finger at $y = 0$ mm and destructive summation from $y = \pm 2$ mm positions. Fairly clean diffraction patterns can be observed at y positions between -25 and -10 mm.

Channel gains of all six objects are compared in Fig. 7. Distance x from Tx plane is 5 mm and the y position is swept from -40 to 40 mm.

Excess attenuations, i.e., excess to the no-object case, are collected to Table I. The *centre* column is for position $(x, y) = (5, 0)$ mm and the *max* column is the any position that maximizes the attenuation with the particular object.

IV. DISCUSSION

- Kyllä, teflonsauva toimii linssinä, kaaviokuva ohessa o Tästä olisi mukava jatkaa eteenpäin, koska käsillä voi olla uusi mittausmenetelmä materiaalin permittiivisyyden karakterisointiin! o Diffraktio on mukana tuloksessa, mutta selkeästi

Fig. 5. Channel gains with the phantom hand at all positions, a 3D illustration.

Fig. 6. Channel gains with the phantom hand at all positions, a 2D illustration.

Fig. 7. Channel gains with all objects at positions $x = 5$ mm and $y = -50 \dots 50$ mm.

TABLE I
MEASURED OBJECTS, THEIR DIMENSIONS AND THE EXCESS
ATTENUATION BOTH IN THE CLOSEST POSITION TO TX AND THE
MAXIMUM ATTENUATION POSITION.

Object	Dimensions [mm]	Attenuation centre [dB]	Attenuation max [dB]
Phantom hand	17 × 14	44.2	44.2
Iron strip	18 × 1.2	41.5	43.0
Stainless steel strip	18 × 1.0	39.3	39.3
Cardboard strip	18 × 0.3	1.5	4.4
Corrugated cardboard strip	18 × 3.5	1.6	6.5
Teflon rod	Ø 26	-3.8	39.6

heikompana kuin sauvan fokusoiva vaikutus o Teflon on ilmeisen vähähäviöinen materiaali käytetyllä taajuudella • Teräsliuska näyttää antavan hienon diffraktiokuvion. Suuremmilla etäisyyksillä diffraktiomaksimit vahvistavat toisiaan $Y[0]$ mm]. • Phantom sormi ei ole aivan symmetrinen, lievä tason nousu $Y[10] - Y[30]$ alueella kertonee heijastuksesta? • Pahvin läpäisyvaimennus on yllättävän pientä, mutta mielenkiintoisesti reuna antaa silti selvän diffraktiovasteen • Kappaleiden mitoista voisi laskea teoreettisia diffraktiokuvioita ja verrata mittauksiin, en tiedä oletko jo tätä tehnytkin

Juurikin tällaista odotinkin näkeväni. Tarkka liike mahdollistaa juuri tämän että näkee esim. tuon diffraktiokuvion mukavasti. Myös tuo linssiefekti on jopa odotettua. Minua kiehtoo jostain syystä kovasti ajatus siitä että erilaisilla asioilla /muodoilla voi olla (ja onkin) suuntaavuutta / vahvistusta ihan luonnostaan, joiden merkitys tulisi vasta näillä korkeilla taajuuksilla oikeasti näkyviin.

Tuo muodon aiheuttama linkin paraneminen on kiinnostava asia, sillä sama objektin objektin pyörähdys aiheuttaa erilaisen signaalitienemisen sekä läpimenevän että heijastuksen. Tämä aiheuttaa, että 6G verkon peitto muuttuu, kun 'mikä' tahansa objekti solussa kääntyy eli tullaan tarvitsemaan todella dynaaminen verkkoiteon optimointi

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Heino, C. Icheln, and K. Haneda, "Finger effect on 60 GHz user device antennas," in *2016 10th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, April 2016.
- [2] J. Medbo and F. Harrysson, "Channel modeling for the stationary UE scenario," in *7th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP 2013)*, April 2013, pp. 2811–2815.
- [3] T. Kürner and S. Priebe, "THz Communications - Status in Research, Standardization and Regulation," *Journal of Infrared, Millimeter, and Terahertz Waves*, vol. 35, pp. 53–62, January 2014.